

Tuning Alya for Energy Efficiency with READEX

Venkatesh Kannan^{a,*}, Ricard Borrell^b, Myles Doyle^a, Guillaume Houzeaux^b

^aIrish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC), Ireland

^bBarcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC), Spain

Abstract

High Performance Computing (HPC) applications are highly complex and demand efficient execution. Energy requirement of current petascale and future exascale systems is a major cause for concern, and it is crucial to improve the energy-efficiency of the applications that run on these systems. A significant source of improvement for applications is that they commonly exhibit dynamic resource requirements. Consequently, such dynamism in an application presents opportunity to tailor the utilisation of resources in the HPC system based on the requirements of the application at runtime. READEX (Runtime Exploitation of Application Dynamism for Energy-efficient eXascale computing) is a EU Horizon 2020 FET-HPC project whose objective is to exploit the dynamism found in HPC applications at runtime to achieve efficient computation on exascale systems. Alya is a high performance computational mechanics application that is present in the Unified European Application Benchmark Suite and the PRACE Accelerator Benchmark Suite. In this paper, we apply the READEX methodology on Alya to identify and exploit any dynamism that is exhibited. We report on the potential energy savings and the effects on the application runtime, where we observe 5-20% reduction in the energy consumed by the application.

1. Introduction

High Performance Computing (HPC) is a major driving force for European research and innovation in many scientific and industrial domains. The applications in these areas are highly complex, and demand high performance and efficient execution. As a result of this growing need for computational performance, the energy consumption of the HPC systems has continued to increase. This is a cause for concern because the energy requirements of current European petascale and future exascale will be a major factor of the total cost of owning HPC systems. Therefore, it is crucial to improve the energy-efficiency of the applications that run on these systems.

A significant source of improvement for applications is that they commonly exhibit dynamic resource requirements. This may stem from different regions in the application that are executed or changes in the workload at runtime. Consequently, such dynamism in an application presents opportunity to tailor the utilisation of resources in HPC systems based on the requirements of the application at runtime. The READEX (Runtime Exploitation of Application Dynamism for Energy-efficient eXascale computing) project leveraged this approach to deliver improved performance and energy-efficiency when executing applications on current petascale and future exascale systems. The goal of the READEX project was to create a tool suite that

1. Identifies existing dynamism in an application to determine its tuning potential.
2. Determines the configurations for different hardware-, system software- and application-level tuning parameters that suit different scenarios that may arise during the application's execution.
3. Applies the best configuration for the tuning parameters during the application's production run.

In this paper, we describe how, as a part of PRACE-5IP WP7, we have chosen to apply the READEX tool suite to identify existing dynamism in the Alya application. When analysing a given application, the READEX tool suite quantifies the application dynamism using *dynamism metrics* such as compute intensity and execution time of the application [1]. The objective of the tool suite is to switch the values for different tuning parameters at runtime to optimal configurations based on the observed application dynamism. We also present the results from our tuning experiments to demonstrate the potential savings that may be achieved when executing Alya using the READEX approach.

In Section 2, we present an overview of the READEX tool suite and the workflow to describe its use. In Section 3, we introduce the Alya application and its relevance to the scientific and HPC community. In

* Corresponding author e-mail: venkatesh.kannan@ichec.ie, telephone: 00353 (0) 1 524 1608

Fig. 1. Overview of READEX methodology

Section 4, we present the steps that were performed to apply READEX on Alya. Section 5 discusses the tuning experiments that were performed to evaluate the potential energy and/or time savings, while we summarise the project with concluding remarks in Section 6.

2. READEX Methodology

The READEX methodology [2] is a tools-aided approach in which the READEX tool suite is applied on a HPC application for automatic energy and performance tuning. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the steps to apply the READEX tool suite on an application are split into two phases: Design time (during application development) and Runtime (during production runs).

2.1 Application Instrumentation and Analysis Preparation

The first step in the READEX methodology is to instrument the HPC application by inserting probe-functions around different regions that are of interest to tuning. A region can be any arbitrary part of the code, for instance a function or a loop. The READEX tool suite is based on instrumentation with Score-P and requires that the *phase region* be manually annotated. A phase region is a single-entry and exit region where most of the application progresses. Typically, a phase region may be the body of the main progress loop of the application. In addition to the phase region, the READEX tool suite supports instrumentation of *user regions* inside the phase region. User regions may be instrumented manually using Score-P or automatically by the compiler.

The READEX methodology also allows exposing parameters that define dynamic behaviour of the application to the READEX tool suite. These parameters, referred to as additional identifiers, will enhance the distinction of different scenarios into runtime situations during the application execution, potentially leading to better identification of optimal configurations for the different tuning parameters. An example of additional identifiers is different input data sets. Exposing this information will allow READEX to detect different compute characteristics of the application caused by different inputs.

2.2 Application Pre-analysis

After instrumenting an application and preparing it for analysis, the second step in the READEX approach is to perform a pre-analysis. The objective of this step is to automatically identify and characterise dynamism in the application behaviour. This is critical because the READEX approach is based on tuning hardware, system and application parameters based on the dynamism exhibited by the different regions in the application. The READEX tool suite is capable of identifying and characterising two types of application dynamism:

- *Inter-phase dynamism*: This occurs when each phase (execution instance) of a phase region in the application exhibits different characteristics. This results in different values for the measured objective values (execution time) and thus may require different configurations to be applied for the tuning parameters for each phase.
- *Intra-phase dynamism*: This occurs when each runtime situation (execution instance) of the significant regions in a phase region exhibits different characteristics and results in different values for the objective

values (execution time and compute intensity). Consequently, this may need different configurations to be applied for the tuning parameters for each runtime situation.

The pre-analysis also identifies the regions in the application that contribute significantly to the execution of an application and are referred to as *significant regions*. If no dynamism is identified in the pre-analysis, then the rest of the READEX steps should be aborted due to homogeneous behaviour of the application since it will not yield any energy or performance savings from auto-tuning.

2.3 Derivation of the Tuning Model

Following the identification of exploitable dynamism in the pre-analysis step, the third step is to explore the space of possible tuning configurations and identify the optimal configurations of the tuning parameters for the phases and runtime instances during the application execution. This analysis is performed by PTF (Periscope Tuning Framework) in conjunction with Score-P and RRL (READEX Runtime Library).

PTF allows for performing design-time analysis experiments through a number of possible search strategies (for example, exhaustive, individual and heuristic search based on genetic algorithm) to identify the optimal configurations for the runtime instances of significant regions (referred to as *rts*) identified in the pre-analysis step that exhibit dynamism. To achieve this, Score-P provides the instrumentation and profiling platform, while the RRL provides the platform for libraries to tune hardware and system parameters. Additionally, the READEX tool suite also has dedicated libraries that allow tuning application-specific parameters.

After all scenarios are explored and optimal configurations are identified, the *rts*' are grouped into a limited number of scenarios, for example up to 20 scenarios. Each scenario is associated with a common system configuration, and it is hence composed of *rts*' with identical or similar best configurations. The limitation in the number of scenarios inhibits a too frequent configuration switching at runtime that may result in higher overheads from auto-tuning. The set of scenarios, information about the *rts*' associated with the scenarios, and the optimal configurations for each scenario are stored by PTF in the form of a serialised text file called the Application Tuning Model (ATM), to be loaded and exploited during production runs at runtime.

2.4 Runtime Application Tuning

Following the completion of design time analysis, production runs of the application can now be tuned at runtime using the optimal configurations summarised in the ATM using the READEX Runtime Library (RRL). The RRL monitors the application execution using the Score-P instrumentation and identifies the scenario that is encountered at runtime. Upon identification of a scenario, the RRL obtains the optimal configurations for this scenario and applies them to optimise the application's energy consumption. The RRL uses libraries that are loaded as plugins for selecting different configurations for the parameters that are tuned by the READEX tool suite.

3. Alya

Alya is a high performance computational mechanics code to solve complex coupled multi-physics, multi-scale and multi-domain problems, mostly coming from the engineering realm. It can handle incompressible/compressible flows, non-linear solid mechanics, chemistry, particle transport, heat transfer, turbulence modelling, electrical propagation and combustion. Alya is used in different application domains such as Bio-Mechanics (heart and respiratory system), Aerodynamics (aeronautics and automotive) or Engineering (combustors, wind farms). Actually, Alya is part of the software hub of three of the Centres of Excellence (CoEs) for computing applications supported by the European Commission, namely: EXCELLERAT, the Centre of Excellence for engineering applications; EoCoE, the centre for energy applications and CompBioMed, focused on the use and development of computational methods for biomedical applications. As a part of these CoEs, Alya was designed to scale on large-scale supercomputers, and is a well-suited candidate for optimisation on future Exascale systems for performant and/or energy-efficient execution.

From scratch, Alya was specially designed for massively parallel supercomputers, and its parallelisation embraces different levels of the computer hierarchy. 1) A sub-structuring technique based on the MPI for distributed memory parallelism [3]. 2) At the node level, both loop and task parallelisms are considered using OpenMP, including dynamic load balancing techniques for a better exploitation of the computational resources. 3) At the CPU level, some kernels are also designed to enable vectorisation [4, 5]. 4) Finally, accelerators like GPUs are also exploited through OpenACC pragmas or with CUDA to further enhance the performance of the code on heterogeneous systems. Alya is one of the twelve-only CFD codes of the Unified European Applications Benchmark Suite (UEBAS) [6] as well as the Accelerator benchmark suite of PRACE [7].

Multi-physics coupling is achieved following a multi-code strategy, by co-executing different instances of Alya [8, 9]. MPI is used to communicate between different instances of the code, which account for different physics. Both implicit and explicit coupling schemes are implemented, as well as conservative interpolation strategies to ensure conservation of the physical properties through the coupling. Thanks to a careful programming strategy, coupled problems can be solved retaining the scalability properties of the individual instances.

In the context of this project, we consider incompressible flow simulations. The physical module solves the Navier-Stokes equations with a 4th order in time fractional step technique, using a low dissipation finite

element method [10]. The pressure equation is symmetric positive definite and solved with a Deflated Conjugate Gradient method [11].

4. READEX on Alya

In order to apply the READEX methodology on Alya, we had to perform three manual steps from the READEX workflow:

1. *Alya instrumentation*: In this step, we identified the code regions in Alya that would be marked as the phase region and user regions for READEX. The details of this step are presented in Section 4.1.
2. *Alya pre-analysis*: In this step, we used the READEX tool suite to detect dynamism expressed by the phase region of any of the user regions that were instrumented in Alya. Section 4.2 presents the results from this step.
3. *Alya tuning parameters*: In this step, we identified the hardware, system-software and application parameters that are to be tuned for Alya at runtime. Details of the tuning parameters to be targeted by READEX for Alya are presented in Section 4.3.

4.1 Alya Instrumentation

The time loop in the file `Alya.f90` is instrumented as the phase region for READEX, and it is the main progress loop of the application. Furthermore, the top ten subroutines in the call tree of Alya with the highest runtime contributions were identified and instrumented as user regions. These are summarised in Table 1. The objective of instrumenting the user regions was to reduce the overhead of energy measurement during the pre-analysis step and experiments to identify the optimal configurations for the tuning parameters using PTF.

File name	Region name
<code>kernel/master/Alya.f90</code>	TIME_LOOP
<code>kernel/domain/mod_matrices.f90</code>	MATRICES_GRADIENT_DIVERGENCE
<code>kernel/domain/mod_matrices.f90</code>	MATRICES_LAPLACIAN
<code>kernel/parall/mod_communications.f90</code>	PAR_BARRIER
<code>kernel/parall/mod_communications.f90</code>	PAR_MIN_4_s
<code>modules/nastin/mod_nsi_schur_operations.f90</code>	NSI_APUVEC
<code>modules/nastin/nsi_dommas.f90</code>	NSI_DOMMAS
<code>modules/nastin/nsi_elmope_all.f90</code>	NSI_ELMOPE_ALL
<code>kernel/solite/defl_cg.f90</code>	DEFLCG
<code>modules/nastin/mod_nsi_eigen_time_step.f90</code>	NSI_EIGEN_TIME_STEP_ELEMENT_OPERATIONS
<code>modules/nastin/mod_nsi_eigen_time_step.f90</code>	NSI_EIGEN_TIME_STEP_ALL
<code>modules/nastin/nsi_bouset.f90</code>	NSI_BOUSET

Table 1. User regions instrumented in Alya

4.2 Alya Pre-Analysis

As described in Section 2.2, the READEX tool suite can analyse a given instrumented application to detect the two types of dynamism. Listing 1 presents a summary of the dynamism detected by READEX when applied on the version of Alya instrumented as described in Section 4.1.

The results include the list of significant regions that are identified along with statistics that include the minimum, maximum and standard deviation of the dynamism metrics (execution time and compute intensity [1]) for the significant regions and phases from the dynamism analysis experiments. Also included are the weights of the dynamism metrics for each significant region as a percentage of the metrics measured for the phase. Based on this, the types of dynamism identified in the application are summarised.

For the Alya application, the dynamism analysis identifies inter-phase dynamism between different iterations of the phase region time loop, intra-phase dynamism in the DEFLCG region due to variation in execution time, and intra-phase dynamism due to variation of compute intensity in regions PAR_BARRIER and DEFLCG.

Listing 1. Summary of Alya pre-analysis

```

...
Candidate regions are:
  TIME_LOOP
  NSI_EIGEN_TIME_STEP_ALL
  PAR_BARRIER
  DEFLCG
  NSI_DOMMAS

Significant regions are:
  DEFLCG
  NSI_DOMMAS

```

```

NSI_EIGEN_TIME_STEP_ALL
PAR_BARRIER

```

Significant region information

```

=====
Region name      Min(t)      Max(t)      Time      Time Dev. (%Reg)  Ops/L3miss  Weight(%Phase)
NSI_EIGEN_TIME_STEP_ALL  0.234      0.245      2.360      1.4            115143011    5
PAR_BARRIER      0.000      1.074      31.029     0.0            0            65
DEFLCG           0.233      0.403      8.355      16.9           4183031     18
NSI_DOMMAS       0.216      0.216      2.159      0.0            200         5

```

Phase information

```

=====
Min              Max              Mean              Time              Dev. (% Phase)  Dyn. (% Phase)
4.45103         7.02546         4.76904          47.6904          0                53.9821

```

```

threshold time variation (percent of mean region time): 10.000000
threshold compute intensity deviation (#ops/L3 miss): 10.000000
threshold region importance (percent of phase exec. time): 10.000000

```

SUMMARY:

```

=====
Inter-phase dynamism due to variation of the execution time of phases

Intra-phase dynamism due to time variation(%) of the following important significant regions
  DEFLCG

Intra-phase dynamism due to variation in the compute intensity of the following important significant regions
  PAR_BARRIER
  DEFLCG

```

4.3 Alya Tuning Parameters

The processor core and uncore frequencies were the hardware parameters tuned by READEX for Alya along with the number of active OpenMP threads for multi-threaded runs of the application. The core frequencies were tuned between 1.2-2.5 GHz, and the uncore frequencies were tuned between 1.2-3.0 GHz in steps of 200 MHz. These are the minimum and maximum values for the processor frequencies, with the default core frequency being 2.5 GHz and default uncore frequency being 3.0 GHz. The number of active OpenMP threads between 1 and maximum permissible depending on the job configuration.

Additionally, a number of application parameters were tuned by READEX using the ACP library (Application Configuration Parameter library). These are summarised in Table 2 and explained below:

- RENUMBERING: Ordering used for the local unknowns defined in the vertices
- GROUPS: Number of degrees of freedom of the coarse system in the Deflated CG algorithm
- COARSE_SOLVER: Direct solver used for the coarse system in the Deflated CG algorithm
- ELEMENT_CHUNK: Chunk size used in the OpenMP dynamic scheduling for the loop around elements
- SOLVER_CHUNK: Chunk size used in the OpenMP dynamic scheduling for the sparse matrix vector product

Application parameter	Range of values	Typical value
RENUMBERING	METIS, CUTHILL_MC_KEE	METIS
GROUPS	100, 200, 400, 800, 1600, 3200	800
COARSE_SOLVER	CHOLESKY, SPARSE	CHOLESKY
ELEMENT_CHUNK	100, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000	400
SOLVER_CHUNK	100, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000	400

Table 2. Alya application tuning parameters

5. Experiments and Results

Based on the tuning parameters that are targeted by READEX as described in Section 4.3, the experiments were conducted on the Taurus cluster at TU Dresden [12] on a partition with Intel Xeon CPU E5-2680 v3 processors, where each node has a 24-core dual-socket setup.

PTF was used to explore the parameter space defined by the different values possible for the application configuration parameters that were listed in Table 2. This was repeated by running the Alya application at

different scales (defined by the number of nodes, number of MPI processes per node and number of active OpenMP threads per process) to obtain the optimal values for the application configuration parameters for each scale.

Following this, production runs of Alya were conducted with increased simulation interval and cycles to measure potential savings in energy consumption and execution time. Two kinds of evaluations were conducted for this evaluation:

- *Homogeneous production runs*: In this case, the production runs of Alya were performed on the same scale for which the optimal tuning parameters were obtained from PTF. These are characterised by the experiments Exp_01, ..., Exp_04 in Table 3 which use tuning models from the corresponding PTF experiments.
- *Heterogeneous production runs*: In this case, the production runs of Alya were performed on scales that were different to the ones for which the optimal tuning parameters were obtained from PTF. These are characterised by the experiments Exp_05, ..., Exp_09 in Table 3 which use tuning models from the PTF experiment Exp_02.

It is important to note that these results are excerpts from the set of experiments that were conducted and are limited here for brevity.

Experiment label	# of nodes	# of MPI processes per node	# of OpenMP threads per process	Tuning model
Exp_01	10	2	12	Exp_01
Exp_02	10	4	6	Exp_02
Exp_03	20	2	12	Exp_03
Exp_04	20	4	6	Exp_04
Exp_05	10	2	12	Exp_02
Exp_06	20	2	12	Exp_02
Exp_07	20	4	6	Exp_02
Exp_08	40	2	12	Exp_02
Exp_09	40	4	6	Exp_02

Table 3. Experiments on Alya with READEX

To evaluate the potential savings in energy consumption and execution time, the production runs of Alya that were performed with the optimal tuning parameters were compared against identically scaled production runs with static values for the tuning parameters that would be typically used by an uninformed end-user. These typical values were provided for the experiments in this project by the application developers. The results of the measured energy and time savings are illustrated in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Figure 2 summarises the savings while using optimal values only for the application configuration parameters (with default values for the processor frequencies and number of OpenMP threads). Here, we observe positive energy and time savings for both homogeneous and heterogeneous production runs and the savings increase with increasing scale of the production runs.

Fig. 2. Energy and time savings for Alya with READEX for tuning application parameters

Fig. 3 presents the savings when using the optimal values for all hardware and software tuning parameters targeted in Section 4.3. Here, we observe that while the energy savings are marginally reduced compared to

when tuning only the application configuration parameters, the execution time savings are drastically reduced. The reason for this is expected to be the overhead from monitoring the significant regions for which hardware and system-software parameters are tuned during the production run. This monitoring is not performed while tuning only the application configuration parameters. This reasoning can be substantiated by performing manual tuning to isolate any possible overhead. However, this requires more efforts than are available within the scope of this mini-project. More details about measuring and mitigating such measurement overheads can be found in the READDEX user guide [13] (particularly, under Section 2.2 on Filtering).

Fig. 3. Energy and time savings for Alya with READDEX for tuning processor frequencies, OpenMP thread count and application parameters

From this, we note that the savings from optimising application tuning parameters are the most rewarding as against tuning hardware and system-software parameters.

6. Conclusions

6.1 Summary

Improved performance and energy efficiency of European HPC applications is of paramount concern for extreme-scale computing systems that are under research and development, and should be of increased concern for PRACE application enablement on the road to Exascale. One approach to address this is to optimise resource utilisation and configure the environment in accordance with the requirements of the application during its execution. The READDEX project aims at developing a tool suite to exploit this approach. The technologies that are developed in READDEX facilitate automatic identification of dynamic resource requirements in an application and tuning hardware, system-software and application parameters for optimised objective values, such as performance and energy consumption.

As described, Alya is one of the most popular and powerful high performance computational mechanics codes to solve complex coupled multi-physics, multi-scale and multi-domain problems, mostly coming from the engineering realm. It is of huge interest to the European and global scientific community which is evident by its presence in multiple benchmark and application suites. Therefore, it is of particular interest in understanding the dynamism and potential optimisations for running this application on extreme scale clusters.

In this paper, we have identified the existing dynamism in Alya and performed a set of experiments, aided by the READDEX tool suite, to identify optimal values for application parameters in addition to the settings for processor core/uncore frequencies and number of OpenMP threads. From these experiments, our evaluations show that energy consumption and execution time savings are achievable between 5-25% on upto 40 node (960 core) runs. These results are indicative of a promising line of action to better understand the reasons for the dynamisms in Alya and pursue further investigations to tune application parameters for different scales of Alya's production runs. A patch for the Score-P instrumentation added to Alya along with the scripts for compilation and execution, and the results presented in this paper are available at [14]. Access to this repository and assistance in using the content can be obtained by contacting the authors of this article at ICHEC.

6.2 Related Work

The ANTAREX project [15] targets efficient performance and energy consumption of applications on heterogeneous Exascale systems that are composed of multi-core CPUs and accelerators. To achieve this, a domain-specific language is designed for expressing adaptivity, energy and performance strategies to enforce runtime

application tuning along with resource and power management. Consequently, an additional compilation step is required to translate the domain-specific language into the target language.

A manual approach to dynamic tuning of parameters was described by Schöne and Molka [16]. This approach extends the VampirTrace framework with a library for users to specify optimal configurations for individual regions, which are later applied at runtime.

The READEX approach is unique and interesting due to automatic analysis and identification of dynamism in an application and its modelling, using tuning experiments performed at design time, to later perform tuning actions during the application's production run.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 730913.

References

1. V. Kannan, L. Říha, M. Gerndt, A. Chowdhury, O. Vysocký, M. Beseda, H. David, R. Sojka, J. Kruzík, and M. Lysaght, "Investigating and exploiting application dynamism for energy-efficient exascale computing," *PRACE 4IP White Paper*, 2017.
2. J. Schuchart, M. Gerndt, P. G. Kjeldsberg, M. Lysaght, D. Horák, L. Říha, A. Gocht, M. Sourouri, M. Kumaraswamy, A. Chowdhury, M. Jahre, K. Diethelm, O. Bouizi, U. S. Mian, J. Kruzík, R. Sojka, M. Beseda, V. Kannan, Z. Bendifallah, D. Hackenberg, and W. E. Nagel, "The READEX formalism for automatic tuning for energy efficiency," *Computing*, vol. 99, no. 8, pp. 727–745, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00607-016-0532-7>
3. M. Vázquez, G. Houzeaux, S. Koric, A. Artigues, J. Aguado-Sierra, R. Arís, D. Mira, H. Calmet, F. Cucchietti, H. Owen, A. Taha, E. D. Burness, J. M. Cela, and M. Valero, "Alya: Multiphysics engineering simulation towards exascale," *J. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 14, pp. 15–27, 2016.
4. G. Houzeaux, R. Borrell, Y. Fournier, M. Garcia, J. Göbber, E. Hachem, V. Mehta, Y. Mesri, H. Owen, and M. Vázquez, "High-performance computing: Dos and don'ts," in *Computational Fluid Dynamics - Basic Instruments and Applications in Science*, A. Ionescu, Ed. Rijeka: InTech, 2018, ch. 01.
5. M. Garcia-Gasulla, G. Houzeaux, R. Ferrer, A. Artigues, V. López, J. Labarta, and M. Vázquez, "Mpi+x: task-based parallelization and dynamic load balance of finite element assembly," *Arxiv*, no. 1805.03949, 2018.
6. "Unified European Applications Benchmark Suite." [Online]. Available: <http://www.prace-ri.eu/ueabs/>
7. "Description of the initial accelerator benchmark suite." [Online]. Available: <http://www.prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/WP212.pdf>
8. G. Houzeaux, M. Garcia-Gasulla, J. Cajas, A. Artigues, E. Olivares, J. Labarta, and M. Vázquez, "Dynamic load balance applied to particle transport in fluids," *IJCFD*, pp. 408–418, 2016.
9. J. Cajas, G. Houzeaux, M. Vázquez, M. Garcia-Gasulla, E. Casoni, H. Calmet, A. Artigues, R. Borrell, O. Lehmkuhl, D. Pastrana, D. Y. nez, R. Pons, and J. Martorell, "Fluid structure interaction based on hpc multi-code coupling," *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. C677–C703, 2018.
10. O. Lehmkuhl, G. Houzeaux, H. Owen, G. Chrysokentis, and I. Rodríguez, "A low-dissipation finite element scheme for scale resolving simulations of turbulent flows," *J. Comp. Phys.*, vol. Submitted, 2018.
11. G. Houzeaux, R. Aubry, and M. Vázquez, "Extension of fractional step techniques for incompressible flows: The preconditioned orthomin(1) for the pressure schur complement," *Computers & Fluids*, vol. 44, pp. 297–313, 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6V26-520J96C-2/2/ab5d4e88c36e26eac7c15f5edfcb159>
12. "Taurus Cluster, TU dresden." [Online]. Available: <https://doc.zih.tu-dresden.de/hpc-wiki/bin/view/Compendium/SystemTaurus>
13. "READEX Tool Suite User Guide." [Online]. Available: https://www.readex.eu/wp-content/uploads/software/readex_toolsuite_user_guide.pdf
14. "READEX applications repository." [Online]. Available: https://git.ichec.ie/readex/readex-apps/tree/master/readex-repository/production_apps/Alya
15. C. Silvano, G. Agosta, S. Cherubin, D. Gadioli, G. Palermo, A. Bartolini, L. Benini, J. Martinovič, M. Palkovič, K. Slaninová, J. a. Bispo, J. a. M. P. Cardoso, R. Abreu, P. Pinto, C. Cavazzoni, N. Sanna, A. R. Beccari, R. Cmar, and E. Rohou, "The ANTAREX approach to autotuning and adaptivity for energy efficient hpc systems," in *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers*, ser. CF '16. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2016, pp. 288–293. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2903150.2903470>
16. R. Schöne and D. Molka, "Integrating performance analysis and energy efficiency optimizations in a unified environment," *Computer Science - Research and Development*, 2014.